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Novel mechanochemical approach for Wheat Starch-LPC complex formationAntoan Rangelov^a, S.Stoyanov^{b,c,d}, L.Arnaudov^b, Tony Spassov^{a*}^aFaculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia University "St. Kl. Ohridski"^bUnilever Research and Development, 3133AT Vlaardingen, The Netherlands^cLaboratory of Physical Chemistry and Colloid Science, Wageningen University, 6703 HB Wageningen, The Netherlands,^dDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, University College London, Torrington Place, London WC1E 7JE, UK**Abstract:**

Amylose-LPC inclusion complexes are acquired by a novel mechanochemical method and by hydrothermal method. The new synthetic method includes mechanical milling of suspension of LPC and starch under controlled conditions. Both methods applied resulted in similar microstructure of the complexes, studied by x-ray diffraction (XRD). Furthermore, Solid-state ¹³C NMR spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) also confirm the efficient complexation by the new approach.

Keywords: amylose-LPC, inclusion complex, ball-milling, DSC

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13 1. Introduction:

14

15 Starch is a biopolymer mixture of predominantly linear amylose and branched amylopectin. It
16 is well known that in the presence of suitable ligand amylose can form a helix with hydrophilic
17 outer surface and hydrophobic inner channel, generally known as V-amylose (Immel and
18 Lichtenthaler, 2000; Morrison et al., 1993). The ligand molecule or a part of it usually resides in
19 the helix, but can also be trapped between helices, to form an inclusion complex with the
20 amylose (Rondeau-Mouro et al., 2004). The V-amylose complexes are known to form with a
21 wide range of ligands such as iodine (Immel and Lichtenthaler, 2000), fatty acids (Godet et al.,
22 1996), potassium hydroxide (Sarko and Biloski, 1980), alcohols (Buléon et al., 1990; Helbert and
23 Chanzy, 1994), flavor compounds (Biais et al., 2006; Nuessli et al., 2003), and other.

24 Lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC) is known to show high complexing ability with amylose, as
25 indicated by DSC (Ahmadi-Abhari, Woortman, Hamer, et al., 2013). Amylose complexation
26 with LPC is shown to change not only the physical properties of starch, but its digestibility as
27 well (Ahmadi-Abhari, Woortman, Oudhuis, et al., 2013).

28 Many methods have been suggested for preparation of V-amylose inclusion complexes. The
29 most frequently used are the classical (Bhosale and Ziegler, 2010; Biliaderis et al., 1985),
30 enzymatic (Kaneko et al., 2008; Kaneko and Kadokawa, 2005), thermo-mechanical (Fanta et al.,
31 2008; Lesmes et al., 2008), and direct mixing (Rachmawati et al., 2013). Kong and Ziegler
32 proposed a method in which “empty” V-amylose or V-starch is prepared followed by “inserting”
33 guest molecules in the preformed helices to form an inclusion complex, indicating that the
34 presence of a ligand is not a must for helix formation (Kong and Ziegler, 2014). Other authors
35 have studied the effect of ball-milling treatment on the physicochemical properties of different

36 starches and have used ball-milling to decrease relative crystallinity and increase the digestibility
37 of starch (He et al., 2014). However, to the best of our knowledge there is no published
38 information on the use of ball-milling for preparation of amylose inclusion complexes.

39 In this work a mechanochemical approach for creating amylose-guest inclusion complexes as
40 alternative to the well-known hydrothermal method was studied. LPC was chosen as a guest
41 molecule because of the high complexing ability and the interesting properties of the amylose-
42 LPC complexes. The new method is simple and allows precise control of the complexing
43 conditions. The synthesis is conducted at ambient temperature so heat sensitive guest molecules
44 could also be used, and the use of typical solvents for starch such as DMSO and KOH is avoided,
45 since the only reactant besides the starch and LPC is water, making this method suitable for the
46 food industry. Also if ball-milling is to be used for industrial treatment of starch, the possibility
47 of inclusion complexes formation with lipids that are naturally present in starch is to be taken
48 into account.

49

50 2. Materials and Methods:

51

52 2.1. Materials

53 The native wheat starch (WS) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (S5127). The
54 Lysophosphatidylcholine (LPC) was purchased from Sigma (L- α -Lysophosphatidylcholine
55 from egg yolk, $\geq 99.0\%$ (TLC)).

56

57 2.2. Complex preparation

58 Two methods for preparation of amylose-LPC inclusion complexes were used. In the
59 mechanochemical approach, starch and LPC (2% w/w) were mixed in a stainless steel
60 reactor, followed by addition of stainless steel balls in ratio 5:1 to the dry mixture. After
61 that water was added so a 10% starch-LPC suspension was obtained. The reactor was
62 sealed and put in a planetary ball mill. Samples were milled for 30 minutes at a time with
63 15 minutes of rest period between millings until the desired total milling time was
64 achieved. 500 rpm were used. The milled suspensions were dried at ambient conditions
65 until constant mass was reached and used for further investigation.

66 In the hydrothermal method starch and LPC (2% w/w) were mixed in a stainless steel
67 reactor. Water was added so a 10% starch-LPC suspension was acquired. The reactor was
68 then sealed and heated for 8 hours at 50°C. After that the suspension was dried at ambient
69 conditions until constant mass was reached and used for further investigation.

70

71 2.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

72 The microstructure of the starch and of the different complexes was determined by
73 Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Co-K α radiation. The XRD scans were taken
74 with a 2 s dwell time and 0.02° step size.

75

76

77 2.4. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

78 DSC thermograms were recorded by a differential scanning calorimeter Perkin Elmer
79 DSC7. Dry samples as described above were weighted in aluminum pans, sealed, left
80 overnight to equilibrate, and then scanned. The scanning rate for all samples was 10 K/min.

81

82 2.5. NMR

83 The NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker HD SB 500 spectrometer (Rheinstetten,
84 Germany) at room temperature using standard Bruker cp pulse program. ^{13}C NMR spectra
85 were recorded at 125.77 MHz using α -glycine at 43.5 ppm as external reference. Solid state
86 ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a 2.5 mm double resonance CPMAS probe-head.

87 Moisture content of the samples was 14.1% for the hydrothermal method complex and 11.6%
88 for the ball-milled complex.

89

90 **3. Results and Discussion**

91

92 Aiming to study the opportunity to use a mechanochemical approach for starch-LPC inclusion
93 complexes formation the intensity and duration of ball-milling a starch/water suspension were
94 varied. The starch to water ratio was the same as for the hydrothermal method, which was also
95 applied in the present study for comparison. In Fig. 1 the XRD patterns of the native wheat
96 starch and of the complexes obtained by the two methods are shown. The optimal conditions for
97 complex formation using the hydrothermal method while preserving the granule integrity was
98 found to be annealing at 50 °C for 8 hours and confirmed the results in (Ahmadi-Abhari, 2013).
99 Further increase in either the temperature or the heating time resulted in gelatinization of the
100 starch which was intentionally avoided. As seen in Fig. 1 the peaks of the native wheat starch
101 were still visible in the XRD pattern of the sample, prepared using the hydrothermal method,
102 which confirms that the granule integrity was successfully preserved. Other authors observed
103 that 1 hour of ball-milling time was enough to significantly decrease the intensities of the
104 diffraction peaks, and after 2 hours of milling no diffraction peaks were visible (Liu et al., 2011).

105 In our case the presence of 2% LPC seemed to have protective effect on the granules and to
106 induce complex formation. The sample prepared by the mechanochemical method for 1h was
107 found to produce XRD pattern very similar to the sample from the hydrothermal method.
108 Increasing the ball-milling times to 5h and 10h led to a decrease in the intensities of the peaks
109 that represent the granule structure, and sharpening as well as intensity increase of the peak at
110 $2\Theta=23^\circ$. In all complex samples the most intensive diffraction peak characteristic for the V-
111 amylose complex could clearly be seen at $2\Theta=23^\circ$, as well as the less intensive peak at about
112 $2\Theta=15^\circ$ was also implied, although not so evidently presented (note that Co $K\alpha$ radiation was
113 used). The characteristic peaks for V-type amylose are seen at $2\Theta=7.4; 12.9; 19.8^\circ$ when using
114 Cu $K\alpha$, respectively $8.6; 14.97; 23^\circ$ when using Co $K\alpha$ (Godet et al., 1996).

115 For proving the complex formation NMR spectroscopy was also applied. The spectra of the
116 complexes obtained by the hydrothermal and the mechanochemical methods are shown in Fig. 2.
117 Both complexes displayed resonances, similar to those reported by other authors for V-amylose
118 complexes (Gidley and Bociek, 1988; Seneviratne and Biliaderis, 1991). For both complexes the
119 peaks observed at 102.7, 81.4, 74.9, 71.9 and 61.6 ppm were respectively assigned to C1, C4,
120 C3, C2-C5, and C6 carbons, characteristic of the V_{61} form (Gidley and Bociek, 1985). The
121 doublet signal in the C1 region of the hydrothermally treated complex could be explained by the
122 presence of non-complexed B-type amylose in addition to the amylose-LPC complex (Gidley
123 and Bociek, 1985; Marchessault et al., 1985). The chemical shifts in the region 95-100 ppm in
124 the ball-milled complex spectra could originate in the presence of less ordered or amorphous
125 complex as indicated by the XRD (Gidley and Bociek, 1988; Le Bail et al., 2005). This could be
126 expected due to the method used for preparation of the complexes and was confirmed by the
127 XRD data. For both complexes a peak at 31.6 ppm was obvious and attributed to the mid-chain

128 methylenes in LPC. Snape et al. used the shift of this peak from 32.5-33.0 ppm, where the
129 chemical shifts of the mid-chain methylenes in crystalline lipids occur (Vanderhart, 1981), to
130 31.6 ppm to confirm the amylose-LPC complexation (Snape et al., 1998).

131 Another efficient method, giving a qualitative as well as a quantitative information concerning
132 the inclusion of LPC into the starch was found to be DSC. Typically DSC of amylose-guest
133 complexes is conducted in the presence of water, which allows the melting endotherms of the
134 complexes to be observed (Le Bail et al., 2005). In our case, however, DSC was performed on
135 complex samples with no addition of water to evaluate the amount of LPC, which participated in
136 the complex formation (Snape et al., 1998). If free lipid molecules were present in the complex
137 samples, prepared via hydrothermal method (b) or mechanochemical method (c, d, and e) an
138 endothermic peak would be observed in the thermogram. The DSC curves of the pure lipid and
139 the complexes are shown in Fig. 3. The thermogram of pure lipid (a) gives a single endothermic
140 peak at 321K with enthalpy of 46.6 J/g which corresponds to melting of LPC. In the DSC curves
141 of the complexes obtained by hydrothermal and mechanochemical methods no melting
142 endotherm could be observed. This could be attributed to the complex formation: the LPC was
143 included in the amylose helices therefore no melting of the LPC could occur, and the V-amylose
144 complexes are stable in this temperature range so no heat effects are visible on the DSC curve.
145 The absence of the melting endotherm at 321K in all complex samples indicates that practically
146 all lipid molecules participated in complex formation. Both preparation methods resulted in total
147 inclusion of LPC, and even 1 hour of ball-milling (c) was found to be enough to produce 100%
148 complexation of added lipid.

149

150 4. Conclusion

151
152 A novel method for Amylose-LPC inclusion complex formation based on ball-milling was
153 developed and compared to the well-established hydrothermal approach. Complexes were
154 characterized by XRD, NMR and DSC. Increase in ball-milling time led to sharpening and
155 increase in intensity of the complex peak at $2\theta=23^\circ$. LPC displayed protective properties in
156 regards to starch granules: even after 10 hours of ball-milling some of the starch peaks could still
157 be observed in the diffractogram, although significantly reduced. Both hydrothermal and
158 mechanochemical methods allowed complexation of the entire amount of added LPC.

159
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163
164 The authors declare no conflict of interest

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234 Figure captions:

235 **Figure 1.** XRD patterns of the native wheat starch (a) and the complexes prepared by: (b)
236 Hydrothermal method for 8h, (c) Mechanochemical method for 1h, (d) Mechanochemical
237 method for 5h, and (e) Mechanochemical method for 10h.

238 **Figure 2:** Solid-state ^{13}C NMR spectra of LPC/Amylose complex obtained by Ball-Milling (red)
239 and by Hydrothermal method (blue).

240 **Figure 3:** DSC curves of native LPC (a), and of the complexes prepared by: (b) Hydrothermal
241 method for 8h, (c) Mechanochemical method for 1h, (d) Mechanochemical method for 5h, and
242 (e) Mechanochemical method for 10h

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- A novel approach for obtaining Starch-LPC inclusion complexes was developed
- The novel method was compared to a well-known technique
- Complex formation was proven with XRD, DSC, and NMR

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